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Impact Of Digitalization On Public Service Delivery In Nigeria: A Case Study Of Federal Civil Service In Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the impact of digitization on public service delivery in Nigeria. Employing a survey research design, questionnaires were distributed across selected federal agencies, namely the Public Service Institute of Nigeria (PSIN), Federal Civil Service Commission (FCSC), and the Federal Ministry of Education (FME). Out of a population of 575, a sample of 381 respondents was targeted, with 369 valid responses received yielding a response rate of 96.85%. Data analysis was conducted using the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) multiple linear regression model, with p-values employed to assess statistical significance. The results indicate that digitization significantly enhances service delivery within the Federal Civil Service. Additionally, the findings highlight ongoing progress in the digitization process across these institutions. The study concludes that digitization contributes to improved efficiency, transparency, and accountability in public service delivery. It recommends increased government investment in digital infrastructure and the promotion of communication technologies to foster a secure, innovative, and efficient public service environment.

Keywords: Automation, digitization, e-governance, internet usage and service delivery

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The beginning of the digital age on the global scale which brought about radical movements towards the increased use of information and communication technology (ICT) in the business world as well as the personal lives of people prompted world governments to join the bandwagon Obi (2020). The dotcom era, which dominated the 1990s, saw the heavy reliance on the World Wide Web and the internet by private sector businesses in their daily business transactions. The high rate of efficiency and accountability which the use of digitization brought into the private sector became a ray of hope for the public sector to redeem their tainted image of inefficiency, lack of transparency and accountability (Ismail, El-Yaqub & Eke, 2025). Thus, the adoption of digitization became an inevitable reform that was bound to be implemented in the provision of public goods and services (Ojo, 2016).

Like any nation in the global community, Nigeria is determined to achieve a standard where digitization becomes the primary mode for carrying out transactions in all spheres of life (El-Yaqub, & Ismail, 2025; Gberevbie, et. al., 2016). Adah (2015) observed that Nigeria has employed various techniques to boost its ICT sector, thereby making Nigeria's telecommunication and ICT sector the fastest growing market in the African continent. He further opined that the country needs to introduce e-governance in all sphere of the society so as to ensure the efficiency of public services and the free flow of information from one sector to another. Based on this reason, the federal government declared ICT as a main concern of national sustainable development; leading to a policy for Information Technology been formulated in 2001 (Oni, et. al., 2016).

The Nigeria government took some noticeable steps to put the country on track in the area of ICT development and utilization in governance (Omeire & Omeire, 2016). The adoption of the National Policy on Information Technology paved the way for e-governance in Nigeria. Some agencies of federal government of Nigeria that have been fully integrated into the e-initiative include; e-passport programme of Nigerian immigration, Abuja Geographical Information System (AGIS) online land registration, National Youth Service Corps (NYSC online), West African Examination Council (WAEC) direct, Joint Admissions and Matriculation Board (JAMB), Automated System for Customs Data (ASTCUDA), National Examination Council (NECO), Post-cash of Nigeria postal service, National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN), Electronic Voters Registrations, on-line payment of fees in most tertiary institutions, On-line display of admission into most Nigerian Universities (Magaji, Ismail, & Musa, 2025; Okwueze, 2015).

However, it was in 2007, that the National Information Technology Development Act of 2007 was later enacted by the National Assembly. The enabling legislation established the National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA), the primary agency saddled with the responsibility of planning, formulating, developing and promoting the use of ICTs in Nigeria (Olatokun & Adebayo, 2015). Between 2011 and 2013, the Nigerian government had adopted various online procedures such as mobile apps and mobile portals to directly support poverty eradication, gender equality, social inclusion and the promotion of economic development, environmental protection and disaster management (Ismail, Musa & Magaji, 2025; Adah, 2015). Many countries in the global community are striving to adopt a new governance strategy that can manage service delivery models in the society. Nigeria is not left out in this global transformation.

In 2003, the Federal Government of Nigeria carried out a Public Service Reform (PSR) study. The result was developing the National Strategy for Public Service Reform (NSPSR) structured in four Pillars and geared towards a systematic restructuring of the Service to meet the challenges of civil rule, democracy, good governance and globalization (Musa & Ismail, 2023). The implementation of the NSPSR started the digitization of the Federal Civil Service in Nigeria (the Financial Management Systems - Integrated Personnel and Payroll Information System (IPPIS), Government Integrated Financial Management Information System (GIFMIS). It was followed by implementing an Electronic Document Management System (EDMS) in the Office of the Head of the Civil Service of the Federation, digitization of the Procurement System.

Today in Nigeria, there is practically no public sector organization that has not undergone one form of reform or the other (Olatokun & Adebayo, 2015). Similarly, following the introduction of modern technology worldwide, there is practically no sector or segment of the society where the influence of Information and Communications technology (ICT) has not penetrated. Most of the reforms that have swept through the public sector in Nigeria include liberalization, deregulation, downsizing, right sizing, commercialization, monetization, privatization (El-Yaqub, Usman, Musa & Ismail, 2024). These reforms are geared towards blurring the line of differences between the public and private sectors, thereby making public service delivery look more business-like. Despite this, public service delivery and accountability are still a far cry in making the public service efficient, flexible, profitable and competitive, many countries have embraced e-governance in their activities (Ogwumike, 2022).

Although digitization is growing in Nigeria in a slow but steady fashion, the emergence of General System for Mobile communication (GSM) network in 2001 contributed to the economic growth of the

country. According to the Nigerian Communication Commission (NCC), the tele density of the country is growing at a tremendous rate (Ojebode, 2017). It was estimated to be above 110 per cent in 2017. However, the ripple effects of these performances have not trickled down to the citizens who are in dire need of a replica of private sector values derived from service delivery. Almost four in five households had mobile phones in 2015; this includes 90 per cent of urban homes and 71 per cent of rural ones. However, based on the E-government Development Index of United Nations Development Economic and Social Affairs (UNDESA), Nigeria scored 0.3291 and ranked in the lower middle class with the likes of Kenya, Iran, Maldives and Indonesia United Nations (2016).

Studies on information technology in Nigeria focused mainly on its ability to serve as a tool for sustainable grassroots development, possible solution to the challenges of the Nigerian public service, as strategy for mitigating non-inclusion of citizens in policy making, possible solution to achieving accountability and the goals of public agencies and assessment of levels and interrelationships of ICT deployment, web readiness and web presence quality of Nigerian e-government websites (Ogunsola & Tiamiyu, 2017). Aluko and Aluko (2015) studied ICT development as a source of comparative advantage in the twenty first century global economy. Oyedele (2017) emphasized on problems such as socio-economic and technological challenges, lack of innovation, incentives, budgetary constraints and inability to identify citizens' needs as challenges facing the public sector in the delivery of public services. Fisher and Gapp (2013) identified problem of inefficient, inequitable, limited access, low quality and ineffective public service delivery in Africa. Therefore, almost twenty-five years into the adoption of digitization for the delivery of public services, there is still much outcry about inefficiency in service delivery in the Federal Civil Service in Nigeria. In the light of the above, the study seeks to examine the effect of e-government on service delivery in the federal civil service in Nigeria. The specific objectives are to assess the effect of e-governance on service delivery; evaluate the effect of automation on service delivery; and investigate the effect of internet usage on service delivery in the Federal Civil Service in Nigeria.

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Digitization

Digitization is the process of taking record materials, typically in the form of papers, and converting them to electronic form where they can be stored and manipulated by a computer (Muturi & Thomas, 2020). Digitization refers to improving processes by leveraging digital technologies and digitized data (Gupta, 2020). Digitization according to Ojo (2014) could be referred to as the application of information communication technology by the government to enhance accountability, create awareness and ensure transparency in the management of government business. It is a political strategy through which the activities of government are made known through the adoption of modern communication technology. Oni, et. al. (2016) stated that digitization constitutes the appropriate use of ICT to achieve the goals of the governments of nations for a reformed public sector and ultimately for improved economic development. Adah (2015) viewed digitization as a broad vision of the utilization of Information and communication technology in government businesses with the primary aim of encouraging greater participation in the state, as well as enhancing the relationship between the government and citizens. Abasilim and Edet (2015) defined digitization as the use of ICTs in the operations of government businesses, put in another way, it is the shift from the traditional method of carrying out government activities which is mainly hierarchical, linear, and one-way to the use of internet which enables the public seek information at their own convenience and not really having to visit the office in person or when government office is open. Cantoni (2015) sees digitization as the use by government agencies of information technologies that have the ability to transform relations with citizens, businesses, and other arms of government. This study adopts the concept of Oni, et. al (2016) defining digitization as the appropriate use of ICT to achieve the goals of the governments of nations for a reformed public sector and ultimately for improved economic development.

2.1.2 Service Delivery

Service delivery simply means the extent to which an individual, unit or department of an organization discharge their assigned or statutory responsibilities (Chukwuemeka, 2017). It is also a means by which an organization evaluates an individual employee or unit input and output level especially in the area of attaining set goals or task assigned. In the view of Byars and Rue (2016) service delivery is the degree to which an employee accomplished the tasks that made his or her job. El-Rufai (2015) summarizes service delivery as the degree of an organization and/or employee performance, output and productivity in the discharge of their responsibilities within the available time, money and other resources, towards the achievement of overall goals of the organization. The spate of service delivery is determined by the performance of employees in achieving organizational goals and satisfying the public. According to Nchuchuwe and Ojo (2017) public service delivery has to do with the provision of those services which are funded by the government. Eigeman (2017) view public service delivery as anything provided to the citizens by the government. He pointed out that public service delivery goes beyond an individual character and looks at the interest of the citizen collective, groups of people. According to Asian Development Bank (2015), public service delivery refers to the provisioning of basic services, such as water, sanitation, and primary education.

2.2 Theoretical Review

2.2.1 Technology Diffusion Theory

The theory emanated from Everett M. Rogers in 1962 who defined diffusion as innovations acceptable and the adoption process by a society or individuals. Diffusion entails five elements that is early adopters, innovators, late majority laggards and early majority. Rogers explains that over time an innovation or an idea acquires impetus therefore spreading by a social system which is specific. Zhang, et. al. (2015) acknowledges that the theory is the usual lens by which theorist carry out study on development and adoption of new ideas. The theory positions that it is easier to implement innovations that show an improved advantage over that which is to be replaced, making it easier to adopt Adegbola (2018). Further it tries to explain how adoption is made to new ideas and innovations by suggesting attributes that have relative advantage when new innovations are seen to be better than the previous one being replaced, the five innovation attributes, are: observability, compatibility, trial ability, relative advantage and complexity (Ouma & Mwangangi, 2018).

2.2.2 Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT)

UTAUT was developed by Venkatesh, Thong and Xu (2016) in the 2000s and is based on social cognitive theory with a combination of eight prominent ICT acceptance research models; the theory of reasoned action (TRA), the theory of planned behaviour (TPB), the technology acceptance model (TAM), the motivational Model (MM), a model combining the technology acceptance model and the theory of planned behaviour (C-TAM-TPB), the model of PC Utilization (MPCU), the innovation diffusion theory (ID) and socio cognitive theory (SCT). UTAUT aims to explain user intentions to use an information system and subsequent usage behavior. Maruping, et al, (2017) affirms that the UTAUT leverages on performance expectancy, effort expectancy, and social influence to predict behavioural intention towards the acceptance of ICT. The theory further proposes that the model constructs are moderated by facilitating conditions and behavioural intention made up of gender, age, experience and voluntariness to predict user behaviour in the acceptance of ICT (Dwivedi, et al, 2019).

Gao, et. al. (2015) highlighted that though UTAUT has not been as widely used as other ICT acceptance research models, it has gradually drawn researchers' attentions, due to its unified perspective and has been recently applied to exploring user acceptance of ICTs. UTAUT integrated and improved the past technology acceptance models and provided a more complete one to explain users' behavioral intention and use behaviour concurs that empirical studies have proved UTAUT is more influential in explaining ICT than others, and this had brought about a great help for the study of technology acceptance. A review of the literature shows that although UTAUT is robust model and many researchers have validated it in different contexts, it is still plagued by limitations that reduce the model's use prediction accuracy. The most important limitation of UTAUT is the large number of independent variables concur that the

exposition of UTAUT is a well-meaning and thoughtful presentation but if not managed well in the end we are left with a model with 41 independent variables for predicting intentions and at least eight independent variables for predicting behaviour” and this can contribute to chaos.

2.2.3 Underpinning Theory

The theory underpinning this study is the technology diffusion theory. The theory provides a vital perspective on one of the most challenging topics within the innovation field, namely, technology assessment, improvement, adoption and implementation thus has become a common reference theory for empirical studies of technological strategies as its strength lies in its utility (Atkin, *et. al.*, 2015). It provides well-developed concepts and a large body of empirical results applicable to the study of technology evaluation, adoption and implementation, provides tools, both quantitative and qualitative, for assessing the likely rate of diffusion of a technology, and additionally, identifies numerous factors that facilitate or hinder technology adoption and implementation. While the theory has been recognized for its role in elucidating technological innovations, limits such as pro-innovation bias have been raised, where the implication that innovations should be diffused to be adopted by all members of a social system, it should be diffused rapidly, and that innovations should be neither re-invented (Hazelman, 2017).

2.3 Empirical Review

Riany (2021) evaluated the influence of e-government strategies on public service delivery of state agencies in Kenya: the moderating effect of strategy execution. The purpose of the study was to examine the influence of E-Government strategy on the public service delivery of state agencies in Kenya. The study adopted a descriptive research design to collect data from the target population comprising of 4230 employees within the management cadre at 132 specific government state agencies incorporated entities outside the mainstream civil service established for purposes of public service delivery in Kenya; 62 Executive Agencies, 25 Independent Regulatory Bodies as well as 45 Research Institutions, Public Universities and Tertiary Education Institutions. Documentary review was also used to compliment the data collected. Convenient sampling technique was used by the study to sample the respondents within the 132 specific government state agencies. Taro Yamani formula was applied to calculate the sample size of 365 employees and self-developed questionnaires were used to collect data from the sample. Data was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The study findings revealed that implementation of E-Commerce, E-Services, E-Administration and E-Participation leads to a significant improvement in the public service delivery of state agencies in Kenya.

Muturi and Thomas (2020) assessed critical success factors of digitization of vital records at civil registration department in Nairobi county, Kenya. According to them many births and deaths go unreported despite there being governing regulations and procedures for notification and registration of these vital events. Aware that the Civil Registration and Vital Statistics (CRVS) system in Kenya has not attained complete coverage of births and deaths, the government is implementing strategies aimed at improving both coverage and quality of vital statistics as outlined in the Civil Registration Department Strategic Plan 2013 - 2017 (Kenya Vital Statistics Report, 2015). The study sought to determine the effect of people-related ICT factors on digitization of vital records at Civil Registration Department in Nairobi County, Kenya. The study focused on Nairobi County as it is the most populated as per the Kenya National Bureau of Statistics (KNBS) census of 2019, has its own civil registration department as well as the department’s headquarters which has copies of all birth and death records from all the other counties. The target population was 100 civil registration officials; four registrars and 96 registration officers from the Ministry of Interior and Coordination of National Government, Civil Registration Department in Nairobi at Bishop’s House-Community.

Adegoroye, *et. al.* (2018) studied the impact of e-government on governance service delivery in Ogun state, Nigeria. The sampling frame comprised of senior and junior staff in three (3) government parastatal (ministries) in Abeokuta, (Ministry of Education, Science and Technology, Ministry of Finance, Ministry of Information and Strategy). The ministries were selected via purposive sampling while the staff were selected at random. 150 questionnaires were administered to the respondents with 125 questionnaires

returned and analyzed using frequency table and percentage analysis. Non-parametric statistical test Chi-square was used to test the formulated hypothesis and the findings showed that e-Government strategies improved service delivery by the public sector in a form of transactional convenience, savings of time and lower service costs which has improved customer's relationship and satisfaction.

Ayoade (2017) studied the impact of information and communication technology (ICT) on public service delivery in local governments, using the three local government councils in Oyo township, as a case study. The study adopted the descriptive survey design methods. Specifically, questionnaires were used to collect data. The population of study constitute of all the staff in the three local government councils in Oyo Township. An incidental random sampling technique was used to select four hundred and fifty (450) respondents from the population of study. Data collected was analyzed using both simple percentage and multiple regression analysis at 0.05 level of significance. The results often showed that there is significant positive effect of ICT on public service delivery. Also, the result indicated that ICT significantly improved public service delivery with regards to cost reduction. The study recommends that provisions should be made for continuous training of the local government personnel on ICT, to keep them informed on new development in information communication technology.

Ewuim and Igbokwe-Ibeto (2016) studied the role of information and communication technology in improving public service delivery, using Amuwo-Odofin local government council of Lagos State, Nigeria, as a case study. They observed that the public service in Nigeria faces challenges associated with corruption, lack of transparency and accountability, high cost of administration and wastage. The study used a combination of survey methods; specifically, personal interview and questionnaires to collect data. Stratified sampling technique was used and data was collected from council staff and their clients. The data was analyzed using tools of inferential statistics. Findings of the work revealed that ICT has significant relationship with delivery of service and that the performance, effective service delivery, transparency and accountability of public service is associated with ICT. Despite this, challenges still abound. The study recommended that the use of ICT should be encouraged and expanded in Amuwo Odofin local government. It also recommended that government should give priority to strategies that increase opportunities for effective and transparent public service delivery.

Arugu and Chigozie (2016) examined the application of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in social and political systems. The study depended mainly on secondary sources of information. The main thrust of the work was to identify the challenges confronting the application of ICT in social and political systems. Findings of the work revealed that power blackouts, the high cost of connectivity and lack of ICT skills ranked highest amongst the challenges identified. Other challenges mentioned include; poor infrastructure, urban-rural digital divide, lack of basic education, obsolete equipment, and high cost of equipment. In line with the findings, and amongst other recommendations, the study suggested that periodic ICT trainings for public servants and unemployed persons should be conducted. Also, it recommended the full digitization of the political and electoral process, in order to ensure effective democratization.

Olokoba, et. al. (2014) studied the impact of Information Communication Technology (ICT) on the management and performance of secondary school teachers in Kwara State, Nigeria. The study posed three research questions. A sample of three hundred teachers (300), from the three senatorial zones in the state was drawn. Questionnaires were used for data collection. Findings of the work showed that many schools do not have ICT facilities, and in places where they are available, teachers do not use the ICT tools in their instructional activities. It was also discovered that the ICT training(s) received by teachers, are not adequate enough for instructional usage. The study recommended that government should partner with private organizations to provide ICT tools for secondary schools in Kwara State, and that needs assessment should be carried out to determine what and types of training, teachers need, before they are selected to go for ICT training.

Ayuba and Aliyu (2014) studied the role of Information Communication Technology (ICT) in combating corrupt business activities in Nigeria. Specifically, they studied how ICT has helped to curtail corrupt practices in business activities within Nigeria. A sample of 200 respondents, representing 70 percent of the population (285) was used for collection of data. The data collected was analyzed using the

descriptive statistics and Chi-Square to test the hypotheses. Findings of the study revealed that ICT helps in reducing spending within the organizations, and increasing earnings. It was also discovered that it helps in identification of ghost workers and elimination of corrupt practices of files and cheques, as well as enhancing marketing practice and tracking of financial fraudsters and other fraudulent banking services, which help to ensure accountability, transparency and effective management. Arising from the findings, the study recommended that both public and private business organizations in Nigeria, should ensure that adequate provision of ICT infrastructure such as access to computers and capacity to connect to the internet globally, and also to ensure that the local communities are involved.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

Survey design was chosen as a result of the distribution of questionnaires administered to Public Service Institute of Nigeria (PSIN), Federal Civil Service Commission (FCSC) and Federal Ministry of Education (FME). This was done with a view to eliciting responses from responses in connection with skills acquisition and entrepreneurship. The study was also quantitative research. A quantitative study was also adopted because the study used mathematical or statistical tools. The adoption of quantitative research was chosen because it is associated with the hypotheses formulated for testing. The target population was 575. The sample size was determined by Yamane (1967). The sample size was 381. Stratified random sampling was the procedure used in this research. This technique was adopted in the study because it points out errors noticed in sampling. In order words, stratified sampling limits bias and boosts the representatives of the various groups in the study. The strata used in classifying staff are: (i) senior management; and (b) middle management. The method of collecting data could be primary and secondary. The use of questionnaire, observation interview and correspondence are the various sources of primary sources of data. The use of questionnaire was adopted because they are effective instrument and permit respondents to willingly state their opinions in relation to research problem. In addition, the study elicits non-parametric information; hence questionnaire was used. The study, the secondary sources were the internet, journals, dissertation amongst several others. The secondary sources were used to review literatures and some other parts of the study.

Descriptive and inferential statistics were applied to analyze the data using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25. This involved use of percentages and frequencies to measure and compare the outcomes. Percentages were used to summarize responses on general information as well as whether or not strategy implementation was practiced in the surveyed firms. Tables have also been used to help explain the research findings. Descriptive tools include mean and standard deviation while multiple linear regression model was employed to see whether the hypotheses were supported by means of correlation analysis and regression analysis. Ordinary least square (OLS) regression method was used for the study as the statistical method for analysing the data gathered. T-test was used to determine whether there is a significant difference between two sets of means. The P-values of results of the multiple regression analysis was used to test for significance of the relationship between variables. The significance level used was 0.05 (5%) to test for significance where any p-value of less than 0.05 indicated a significant relationship.

The study adopted multiple regression analysis to examine the effect of the independent variables of the variation on dependent variable. The functional relationship between variables in this study is therefore, the implementation of skills and entrepreneurial development is a function of self-employment, increased income generation of civil servants in Nigeria; poverty reduction and future benefits of federal civil servants in Nigeria. However, to show how well the model containing those of five explanatory variables actually explains the variations in the dependent variable (skills acquisition and entrepreneurial development) it is necessary to test it through goodness of fit statistic.

Table 1: Goodness of Fit through R²

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.956	0.961	0.808	0.496

Source: SPSS Regression Result, 2024

Table 1 above summarizes the information about the variation of the dependent variable explained by the existing model used for this study and the residual that indicates the variation of the dependent variable that are not captured by the model. Both R^2 and adjusted R^2 measure the fitness of the model. Furthermore, the table revealed that $R = 0.956$, $R^2 = 0.961$ and adjusted $R^2 = 0.808$. The adjusted R^2 in this study is less than the R^2 which indicates that the independent variables improve by less than expected by chance. An R^2 of 0.961 implies that 96.1% of changes in service delivery in the Federal Civil Service in Nigeria are explained by the independent variables of the study. There are however other factors that influence digitization and service delivery that are not included in the model which account for 3.9%. An R of 0.956 on the other hand signifies strong positive correlation between the variables of the study.

Table 4.2: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

Model	SS	df	MS	F	Significance
Regression	568.24	5	570.4	676.015	0.0812
Residual	351.40	431	0.950		
Total	919.64				

Source: Field Data, 2024

From Table 4.2, ANOVA table above, the value of F calculated is 676.015 while F critical is 499.465. Since the value of F calculated is greater than F critical, the overall regression model was significant and therefore a reliable indicator of the study findings. In terms of p values, the study indicated 0.001 which is less than 0.05 and therefore statistically significant.

Table 4.33: Regression Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T- test	p-value
	B	Standard Error	Beta		
Constant	8.28	0.574		8.012	0.000
E-governance	0.955	0.022	0.811	14.15	0.000
Automation	0.876	0.033	0.120	11.04	0.000
Internet usage	0.745	0.029	0.127	1.15	0.000

Source: SPSS Regression Result

The first objective was to assess the effect of e-governance on service delivery. The multiple regression result showed that the first parameter estimate, e-governance has a positively strong correlation (0.955) with service delivery in the Federal Civil Service in Nigeria. The statistical significance (p value) gives 0.000. This implies that e-governance has statistical effect on service delivery in the Federal Civil Service in Nigeria.

The second objective was to assess the effect of automation on service delivery. The multiple regression result showed that the first parameter estimate, e-governance has a positively strong correlation (0.876) with service delivery in the Federal Civil Service in Nigeria. The statistical significance (p value) gives 0.000. This implies that automation has statistical effect on service delivery in the Federal Civil Service in Nigeria.

The third objective was to assess the effect of internet usage on service delivery. The multiple regression result showed that the first parameter estimate, e-governance has a positively strong correlation (0.745) with service delivery in the Federal Civil Service in Nigeria. The statistical significance (p value) gives 0.000. This implies that internet usage has statistical effect on service delivery in the Federal Civil Service in Nigeria.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study examines the effect of digitization on service delivery in the Federal Civil Service in Nigeria. The study also revealed that there is progress in digitization of Federal Civil Service in Nigeria. Digitization ensures effectiveness in service delivery in the Federal Civil Service improves clarity and

openness in the Federal Civil Service. Digitization reduces turnaround time in service delivery in the Federal Civil Service. Digitization increases customer satisfaction through provision of value-adding services or products in service delivery and boosts efficiency in allocation of institutional resources in service delivery in the Federal Civil Service. The adoption of Digitization makes service delivery, inclusive, efficient, responsive, transparent, accountable and more participatory which embodies the elements of good governance at local level. Application of modern technologies may facilitate the current struggle against corruption in the Federal Civil Service.

Based on the findings, the study recommends that:

- i. Federal Civil Service in Nigeria (Ministries, Departments and Agencies) should show a high level of willingness and knowledge in their operations. Government should ensure that all offices are equipped with functional computers, employ highly skilled personnel in ICT, provision of continuous training of the personnel to keep them informed on how best to utilize automation in engendering effective service delivery in the Federal Civil Service in Nigeria.
- ii. The Federal Civil Service must provide the necessary infrastructure that will aid the successful implementation of internet usage in the Federal Civil Service in Nigeria. Robust broadband services, required internet network and the availability of power supply, which has been identified as one of the major challenges to digitization in the public service has to be taken care of. This means that the success of internet usage implementation in the public service is tied to the availability of power supply and in this case electricity. Government offices must also be connected to internet, with trained and qualified staff.
- iii. Government should increase its investment in digitization of public organisations. Promoting communication technology will foster a secure and innovative digital environment thereby contributing to service delivery.

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